

agents of various types have been used for separating transition and inner-transition metal ions⁸⁻⁹. Attempts have been made to use glycolic acid as its aqueous solution to provide potent complexing media for such studies and the results are presented here. As the pH of the electrolyte plays an important part in modifying the migration trends of metal ions, the use of suitably buffered solutions at fixed pH values have been done to study the electromigration of some 14 metal ions by horizontal electro-phoretic method.

Experimental

Aqueous 1, 1.4, 2, 4, 5 and 7% (w/v) solutions of glycolic acid (Riedel, W. Germany) were prepared and used as electrolytes at definite pH values. The pH of these solutions was adjusted with ammonia solution using a pH meter.

Stock solutions (0.1 M) of Fe²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺, Pb²⁺, Ag⁺, Tl⁺, Th⁴⁺, UO₂²⁺ as nitrate and Ti²⁺, Mn²⁺, Hg²⁺, Zn²⁺ as chlorides were prepared from A.R. reagents. Working solutions containing 3-10 µg/µl were prepared by dilution.

The chromogenic reagents employed for detection of metal ions were (a) rubeanic acid, (b) alizarin red-S, (c) chromotropic acid, (d) rubeanic acid/salicylaldoxime/alizarin mixture, (e) yellow ammonium sulphide and (f) potassium ferrocyanide.

Whatman No. 1 filter paper strips of 2 cm x 35 cm were used for electromigration of metal ions at 5V/cm potential gradient for 2 hr. Many separations have been carried out successfully in aqueous glycolic acid media suitably buffered. These have been reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION OF TERNARY, QUATERNARY AND POLYINARY METAL ION MIXTURES

Electrolyte % w/v	Mixture	Position on paper strip		
		Cationic (-)	Iso-electric	Anionic (+)
Glycolic acid (aq.) 1.4% at pH 4	Fe-Co-Cu	Co Cu Fe		
	Fe-Ni-Cu	Ni Cu Fe		
	Fe-Co-Ag	Co Fe	Ag	
	Fe-Ni-Ag	Ni Fe	Ag	
	Fe-Cu-Ag	Cu Fe	Ag	
	Ni-Cu-Ag	Ni Cu	Ag	
	Co-Cu-Ag	Co Cu	Ag	
Glycolic acid (aq.) 4% at pH 2	Ti-Fe-Co	Co Fe Ti		
	Ti-Fe-Ni	Ni Fe Ti		
	Ti-Fe-Cu	Cu Fe Ti		
	Ti-Fe-Cd	Cd Fe Ti		
	Ti-Fe-Hg	Fe Ti		Hg
	Ti-Fe-UO ₂	UO ₂ Fe		Ti
	Ti-Co-Cu	Co Cu Ti		
	Ti-Co-Hg	Co Ti		Hg
	Ti-Ni-Cu	Ni Cu		Ti
	Ti-Cu-Hg	Cu Ti		Hg
	Ti-Ni-Hg	Ni Ti		Hg
	UO ₂ -Co-Hg	Co UO ₂		Hg
	UO ₂ -Ni-Hg	Ni UO ₂		Hg
	UO ₂ -Cu-Hg	Cu UO ₂		Hg

Table 1 (Contd.)

Glycolic acid (aq.) 4% at pH 2	Ti-Fe-Cu-Hg	Cu Fe Ti		Hg
	Ti-Fe-Cu-Ag-Hg	Cu Fe Ti	Ag	Hg
	Ti-Fe-Co-Cu-Hg	Co Cu Fe Ti		Hg
	Ti-Fe-Ni-Cu-Hg	Ni Cu Fe Ti		Hg
Glycolic acid (aq.) 2% at pH 4	Hg-Ti-Fe-Co-Cu-Ag	Co Cu Fe Ti	Ag	Hg
	Ti-Fe-Ni-Cu-Ag-Hg	Ni Cu Fe Ti	Ag	Hg
	Fe-Ti-Mn	Mn		Fe Ti
Glycolic acid (aq.) 2% at pH 6	Ti-Pb-Hg	Ti Pb	Pb	Hg
	Ag-Ti-Hg	Ti	Ag	Hg
	Mn-Fe-Zn	Mn		Fe Zn
Glycolic acid (aq.) 5% at pH 6	Ti-Pb-Hg	Ti	Pb	Hg
	Ag-Ti-Hg	Ti	Ag	Hg
	Fe-Mn-Zn	Mn	Fe	Zn

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Kinetics of Oxidation of L-Rhamnose by Vanadium(V)

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KINETICS of oxidation of hexoses¹⁻³ and pentoses⁴ by vanadium(V) have been reported earlier. We are now reporting that of L-rhamnose, a deoxy sugar, in sulphuric acid medium.

Experimental and Results

The kinetics of reaction has been studied under the condition [L-rhamnose] and [H₂SO₄] ≫ [vanadium(V)]. Other details are the same as described earlier⁴.

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Fig. 1

Variation of pseudo first order rate constant k_1 (sec^{-1}) with $[\text{L-rhamnose}]$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ is given in Table 1.

TABLE I—VARIATION OF k_1 WITH $[\text{L-RHAMNOSE}]$ AND $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ AT 65° . VANADIUM(V) = $6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$

$[\text{L-Rhamnose}] \times 10 \text{ M}$	$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] \text{ M}$	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
0.66	1.25	0.75 ± 0.08
1.33	1.25	1.24 ± 0.11
2.00	1.25	1.84 ± 0.17
2.66	1.25	2.81 ± 0.12
3.33	1.25	2.77 ± 0.22
0.66	0.10	0.42 ± 0.07
0.66	1.25	0.75 ± 0.08
0.66	2.39	1.16 ± 0.08
0.66	3.53	1.37 ± 0.04
0.66	4.68	2.17 ± 0.14
0.66	5.82	3.06 ± 0.12
0.66	6.99	4.34 ± 0.34

A plot of $1/k_1$ against $1/[\text{L-rhamnose}]$ gives a straight line with an intercept (cf Fig. 1) suggesting the complex formation between vanadium(V) and L-rhamnose. The value of equilibrium constant K has been computed as 1.61×10^4 . k_1 depends on $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ as 1.07 slope value is obtained from $\log k_1$ and $\log [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ plot. Zucker-Hammett⁵, Bunnett⁶ and Bunnett-Olsen⁷ plots were obtained with slope values as -0.27 , 4.3 (w) and 0.98 (ϕ)

respectively. k_1 has also been found to increase from $0.42 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ to $6.29 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ when % composition of acetic acid-water mixture was varied from 0-60% at $[\text{vanadium(V)}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{L-rhamnose}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.10 \text{ M}$ and temperature 65° .

From the variation of k_1 with temperature, the thermodynamic parameters are obtained as:

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = 26.76 \pm 0.09 \text{ Kcal mole}^{-1}, \Delta S^\ddagger = 1.98 \pm 0.23 \text{ e.u. and } \Delta G^\ddagger = 26.04 \pm 0.20 \text{ Kcal mole}^{-1}.$$

Discussion

Vanadium(V) exists as $\text{VO}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}^+$ or $\text{V}(\text{OH})_2^+$ in acidic medium⁸. The active species formation can be expressed as⁹

The following reaction steps can now be proposed:

where $\bar{R}$ = free radical (confirmed by induced polymerisation with acryl nitrile) and $kf \gg ks$

The final rate law thus can be derived as :

$$-\frac{d[V(V)]}{dt} = \frac{2ksK_1K[VO_2 \cdot 2H_2O^+][L\text{-Rhamnose}][H_2SO_4]}{1 + K[L\text{-Rhamnose}]} \dots (4)$$

Due to coordination, the activation energy for C-C bond rupture is lowered¹⁰ and this is in agreement with the observed value of $\Delta H^\ddagger$. Further, the unimolecular disproportionation of complex proposed in step 3 is consistent with the observed small value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$.

Thus, the proposed steps (1-3) and rate law (4) incorporate the kinetic results satisfactorily.

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Potentiometric Determination of Dissociation Constants of DL-Tryptophan in Different Aquo-Organic Solvents

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In continuation of our earlier work on metal-amino acid complexes^{1,2}, this communication reports the dissociation constant (pK) of DL-tryptophan at constant ionic strength in different aquo-organic solvents (20%, v/v) viz., acetone, acetonitrile, iso-propanol, N,N-dimethyl formamide, *n*-butanol and dimethyl sulfoxide by Albert Serjeant³ method.

Experimental

DL-Tryptophan was obtained from BDH and all other solvents were of AnalaR grade. pH measurements were made on a Toshniwal digital pH meter (accuracy ± 0.1 pH) with glass calomel electrode assembly. The temperature of the cell was maintained by a thermostat (U_s -type, German) having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

For determining the pK of DL-tryptophan (HA) the calculated amount of the HA corresponding to 0.01 M per 25 ml solution is dissolved in 20% solvent and 0.1 M $NaClO_4$ (giving a total volume of 22.5 ml). It was titrated against 0.1 M $NaOH$ in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen and the pH was recorded as equilibrium reached after each addition⁴. The pK values of $\overset{+}{N}H_2CHCOO^-$ group of DL-tryptophan determined in different solvents (20%, v/v) at $25^\circ \pm 0.1$ and $\mu = 0.1$ M $NaClO_4$ are given in Table 1 and follow the order: N,N-dimethyl formamide (9.24) > dimethyl sulfoxide (9.19) > acetone (9.15) > iso-propanol (9.14) > acetonitrile (9.08) > water (9.02) > *n*-butanol (8.96).

This variation in values may be partly due to the change in dielectric constant⁵ of the medium which depends on the viscosity and ionic interaction in solutions⁶.

TABLE 1—THE pK VALUES OF DL-TRYPTOPHAN IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS (20%, v/v) AT $25^\circ \pm 0.1$ AND $\mu = 0.1$ M $NaClO_4$.

Titrant 0.1N $NaOH$ ml	A		B		C		D		E		F		G	
	pH	pK												
0.0	6.75	—	5.70	—	6.48	—	6.54	—	6.50	—	6.96	—	4.60	—
0.5	8.57	9.17	8.45	9.05	8.45	9.05	8.44	9.04	8.87	8.97	8.34	8.94	8.32	8.92
1.0	9.00	9.17	8.98	9.16	8.90	9.07	8.89	9.07	8.86	9.04	8.81	8.98	8.82	8.96
1.5	9.87	9.20	9.82	9.15	9.27	9.10	9.27	9.10	9.28	9.11	9.18	9.25	9.20	9.03
2.0	9.76	9.20	9.72	9.15	9.70	9.18	9.67	9.10	9.70	9.18	9.59	9.02	9.55	8.98
2.5	10.48	9.48	10.45	9.45	10.40	9.40	10.38	9.39	10.48	9.15	10.22	8.91	10.28	8.94
Mean	—	9.24	—	9.19	—	9.15	—	9.14	—	9.08	—	9.02	—	8.96

A = N,N-dimethyl formamide; B = dimethyl sulfoxide; C = acetone; D = iso-propanol; E = acetonitrile;
F = water; G = *n*-butanol.